

A QUANTITATIVE INVESTIGATION INTO THE EFFECT OF PROCESSING CONDITIONS AND MOULDING THICKNESS ON FIBRE ORIENTATION IN SHORT FIBRE-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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SUMMARY: This paper reports on work which is being done to develop & use automated procedures for measuring 3D fibre orientation distribution (FOD) quantitatively in short fibre reinforced thermoplastics (SFRTPs). Through-thickness images comprising about 3000 fibres from polished sections are acquired using a CCD camera mounted on an optical-reflective microscope. Orientation is described in the form of weighted second order tensor components, in which the measurement errors, mainly resulting from the misalignment of the specimen, are included to provide upper & lower bounds. The whole process is automated and allows large numbers of images to be processed and analysed rapidly. The effects of mould geometry and processing conditions on FOD in 20% GFPP(Glass fibre reinforced polypropylene) mouldings have been studied. Results are shown of the variation of fibre orientation through the thickness at specific positions, and for complete cross-sections, the latter incorporating more than 150,000 fibres. Final orientation distribution is complex and depends on such factors as relative dominance of divergent or shear flow conditions, rate of flow and cooling effects.

KEYWORDS: injection moulding, short fibre, fibre orientation distribution, polypropylene, image processing, injection speed, moulding thickness

INTRODUCTION

Many experimental studies [1,2] have shown that fibre orientation distribution (FOD) in short fibre-reinforced thermoplastics (SFRTPs), and consequent mechanical properties, depend on the flow conditions in the mould. In order to design with SFRTPs more effectively, a thorough understanding of FOD in a quantitative way is paramount. One aim of this paper is to describe the use of an automated image processing and analysis system for the accurate quantitative measurement of FOD. A second aim is to develop a greater understanding for the effects of position, injection speed and moulding thickness on FOD. The paper presents results from FOD measurements through the cross-section of 20%GF/PP rectangular plaques and discusses these results in terms of the complex flow field generated in such plaques.

EXPERIMENTAL

Test Plaque Production

The material used in this study is 20 wt% glass filled polypropylene, injection moulded in a specially designed mould with inserts to allow different geometries and thicknesses. Nominal rectangular plaques, 150 mm x 50 mm in size and of 2 mm and 4 mm thicknesses have been moulded as shown in Fig. 1. Each plaque is fed through a 2 mm x 2 mm pin gate. Typical processing temperatures are given in table 1 and cavity fill times of 1, 3 and 10 seconds have been studied, corresponding to nominal injection speeds of 150, 50 and 15 mm/s respectively.

Table 1 : Processing temperatures for the moulding of 20% GF/PP rectangular plaques

Mould Temperature	Barrel Temperature		
	Front	Middle	Rear
50° C	260° C	240° C	230° C

Although the development of orientation in other more complex geometries has been studied [3], simple rectangular plaques were chosen to focus on the effect of processing conditions.

Measurement Positions and specimen Preparation

Detailed through-thickness fibre orientation distribution (FOD) has been measured at two primary positions, A and B, as shown in Fig. 1. Position A is 25mm from the gate at the centre of the plaque, whereas position B is half way along the plaque, i.e. 75 mm from the gate, again at the centre. Specimens for measurement are cut from the plaque at the relevant position and cast in polyester resin. Careful grinding is then performed in an automatic machine using water-proof silicon carbide papers through grades of 250, 400, 800, 1200 and 4000. Finally, the specimen is polished using 1µm aluminium paste.

Fig. 1 Pin-gated plaque and positions where fibre orientation distribution is measured.

Image Acquisition

A Vickers microscope equipped with a 768x512 array CCD camera coupled directly to a PC is used for image acquisition. The magnification should be such that the smallest fibre diameter can be resolved and yet still present a sufficiently large field of view. A magnification of 100 is selected, giving a maximum resolution of 1.124 µm per pixel. For detailed measurements through the thickness of a 4mm plaque at each position two columns of 13 frames, each 0.860x0.287mm, are captured, amounting to at least 3000 fibres. In some cases, data from a full cross-section of the plaque is obtained where there may be in excess of 100,000 fibres.

IMAGE PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

Image Processing Algorithms

Image processing is conducted using the function libraries of a proprietary package, Visilog®, in conjunction with purpose developed algorithms. Details are given in [4,5,6]. A top-hat transformation, based on grey-scale morphological operations, is used to separate the peak (white-grey fibre) from the valleys (dark-grey matrix), at the same time dealing with uneven illumination and poor contrast. The process involves eroding and dilating the image for N iterations, in which N is in the range D-1.4D, where D is the nominal fibre diameter in pixels. The resulting image is finally subtracted from the original image. After the subtraction, an Entropy function is used to threshold the image to a binary format. The connected fibres are then separated by producing a Distance Map on which a Watershed algorithm operates. The Distance Map is a map of the image, in which the brightness of a grey pixel is a measure of the distance of the corresponding binary pixel from the outer periphery of the feature. This creates a grey scale image of peaks and valleys and watershedding can separate these into distinct features. Different watersheds are set for identifying isolated particles and for segmentation of connected particles. Finally, all the separated fibres are labelled and assigned a number. The whole process is fully automated.

Pattern Recognition

Fibre cross-sections appear as circles and ellipses in the image. The three-dimensional orientation state, as defined by the two angles, θ (in-plane), and ϕ (out-of-plane), is calculated from the length of the major and minor axes of each ellipse, in addition to the angle the major axis makes with the x-axis in the image co-ordinate system. The length of the major and minor axes are derived from the second moments of area of each individual ellipse using Visilog® area moment functions. The in-plane angle θ is given by, minor

$$\frac{\text{Length of the minor axis}}{\text{Length of the major axis}} = \frac{I_{min}}{I_{max}} = \frac{\frac{I_{xx} + I_{yy}}{2} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{I_{xx} - I_{yy}}{2}\right)^2 + I_{xy}^2}}{\frac{I_{xx} + I_{yy}}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{I_{xx} - I_{yy}}{2}\right)^2 + I_{xy}^2}} \quad (1)$$

where I_{xx} , I_{yy} and I_{xy} are the second moments of area of the ellipse about the x and y axes.

The out-of-plane angle ϕ is calculated from the angle the major axis of the ellipse makes with the x-axis, and is given by the following expression,

$$\tan(2\phi) = -\frac{2I_{xy}}{I_{xx} - I_{yy}} \quad (2)$$

This equation leads to two values of ϕ , 90 degrees apart. The correct value is found by back substituting into the expressions for the principal second moments and checking for consistency with the values above.

Tensor Representation of Fibre Orientation Distribution (FOD)

The orientation tensor has been shown to be a concise method of describing the average orientation state of a number of fibres [7]. The orientation angles are used as input to form the tensor components. In addition, it is necessary to weight the contribution of each fibre to the average tensor component, according to its ellipticity [7]. This takes into account the probability of cutting each fibre. The weight average second order orientation tensor components are then given by,

$$a_{ij} = \frac{\sum (a_{ij})_n \frac{I}{\cos \theta_n}}{\sum \frac{I}{\cos \theta_n}} \quad (3)$$

a_{11} & a_{22} are measures of the in-plane orientation in the flow direction & transverse to the flow direction respectively, whilst a_{33} is an indication of out-of-plane orientation.

Bounds on the Results

The major source of measurement error arises from misalignment of the section plane of the specimen. For a misalignment angle α , denoting a clockwise rotation about the 3 axis, the actual orientation angles can be computed from measured angles [8] using the following transformation expressions,

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \theta &= -\sin \alpha \sin \theta_\alpha \cos \phi_\alpha + \cos \alpha \cos \theta_\alpha \\ \cos \phi &= (\cos \alpha \sin \theta_\alpha \cos \phi_\alpha + \sin \alpha \cos \theta_\alpha) / \sin \theta \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where α = misalignment angle; $\theta_\alpha, \phi_\alpha$ = measured values; θ, ϕ = actual values

The specimen preparation procedure should align the section plane to within 2 degrees. A conservative estimate of the upper and lower bounds on the orientation tensor components has therefore been made by assuming the misalignment angle to be $\alpha = \pm 2.5$ degrees. These bounds are included in the graphical results presented in the following sections.

RESULTS

Effect of Position in the Plaque

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show through-thickness photographs taken at position A (gate) and position B (centre) of a 2mm plaque moulded at 1 second fill time i.e. high speed. Fig.4 shows the corresponding quantitative measure of through-thickness FOD at these two positions. It is clear from the photographs that there is a significant reduction in the thickness of the transversely aligned core layer at position B, a fact confirmed by the measurements shown in Fig. 4. The high values of a_{11} in layers 2-3 and 11-12 ($a_{11} > 0.6$), also shown in Fig. 4, are indicative of shear alignment in the high shear region adjacent to the frozen layers. By contrast, in these outer frozen layers, the value of a_{11} reduces as a result of the rapid cooling of the melt and corresponding increase in viscosity, which limits the amount of shear alignment that can take place. Throughout the thickness, at both positions A and B, a_{33} remains low, showing that the flow is largely in-plane in all layers. However, a_{33} values are

marginally higher away from the central core layers, possibly indicating the drag affect of the frozen layer causing some fibres to move out of plane.

As the polymer melt enters the cavity through the constricted pin gate, divergent flow will tend to align the fibres in the transverse direction giving the observed wide core region at position A. As the melt moves down the plaque the shear forces take affect on the outer layers causing greater alignment in these regions and the observed narrower core. Without the influence of shear forces, the transverse alignment in the central core is retained even at position B.

Fig.2 A through-thickness image of the 2mm plaque at position A.

Fig.3 A through-thickness image of the 2mm plaque at position B.

Fig.4: Measured through-thickness orientation tensor components near the gate (position A) and at the centre (position B) of the 2mm plaque at 1s. injection time.

Fig. 5: Measured through-thickness orientation tensor components for the 4mm plaque at position B for different injection speeds (1s, 3s and 10s fill times)

Effect of Injection Speed

4 mm Plaque

Fig.5 shows the variation of tensor components, a_{11} and a_{33} , at position B (middle) in the 4 mm plaque, for three injection times; 1, 3, and 10 seconds. In general, the results show that injection speed over this range has little effect on the FOD. There is some evidence of a greater transverse alignment in the core region at high injection speed and a more abrupt change from high skin values to low core values at this speed. These observations may be a consequence of the blunter velocity profile arising from greater shear thinning in this case. The a_{33} values remain low throughout the thickness, again indicative of very little out-of-plane alignment apart, that is, from an increase in the core region at slow filling time. The origin of this out-of-plane alignment is uncertain.

Fig.6: Measured orientation tensor components across the width of the 4mm plaque at position B for 1s and 10s injection times

Fig.7 Measured through-thickness orientation tensor components for the 2mm plaque at position B for 1s injection times.

A further study of the effects of processing speed has been made by measuring the orientation in the two central through-thickness layers, i.e. 2/13th of the plaque thickness, across the full width of the 4 mm plaque at position B. The results are shown in Fig. 6 for two injection fill times (1s and 10s). Although there is some scatter in the measurements, it is clear that a similar pattern of FOD occurs across the width to that already seen through the thickness. Low a_{11} values occur at the centre of the plaque width, rising gradually to high values at the edges. The pattern appears to reflect the curved nature of the flow front across the width. It is also interesting to see that the a_{33} component remains low for much of the width, indicating in-plane flow, but rises to quite a high value (~ 0.3) near the plaque edges. This out of plane

alignment is likely to be caused by the fountain flow freezing onto the walls in these regions where the proximity of three mould surfaces increases the cooling rate.

As with the through-thickness results, injection speed only has a marginal effect on the cross-width results, however, a pattern is discernible. At high injection speed (1s fill time) there appears to be more of a distinction between the a_{11} values near the edge and those in the centre than there is at low injection speeds. There is a clear cross over of the a_{11} lines for the two speeds in the regions of column 17 and 27 in Fig. 5. One explanation for this is that at the higher speed the cross width flow front may be blunter due to the greater shear thinning. However, it should be pointed out that any such differences in flow front geometry have yet to be measured.

2 mm Plaque

Fig. 7 shows the through thickness FOD at position B for the 2 mm plaque at two injection speeds; 1 and 3 second fill times. At the higher injection speed (1s) a_{11} is higher in the skin regions which is a consequence of the higher shearing in this case. It is also apparent that the core region is wider for the high speed injection which could be related to the degree of cooling. At the low injection speed (3s), by the time the melt has reached the middle of the plaque (point B), it will have cooled more than it does under high speed injection conditions. This will result in a wider frozen layer, a shear region closer to the mid plane and a consequent reduced core region. In contrast to the 4 mm plaque, because of these cooling effects, the effect of injection speed is more pronounced in the thinner 2 mm plaque.

Effect of Thickness

Fast Injection Speed (1s fill time)

Figs. 8 and 9 show detailed contour plots of the a_{11} tensor component for full cross-sections at position B for both the 4 mm and 2 mm plaques. Both plaques have been moulded at high injection speed. It is important to note the complexity of the orientation.

Fig.8 Cross-sectional Contour plot of a_{11} halfway along the 4mm plaque (X-width Y-, thickness); 1 second injection time.

Fig. 9 Cross-sectional contour plot of a_{11} halfway along the 2mm plaque (X-width, Y-thickness); 1 second injection time.

The general skin-core structure extends throughout the cross-section of both plaques, both through the thickness and across the width. Although the low orientation contour ($a_{11} = 0.15 - 0.225$) indicates a relatively smaller core for the 2 mm plaque, particularly across the width, the mid range contour ($a_{11} = 0.375 - 0.45$) tells a very different story. This contour, which is more indicative of the transition from longitudinal to transverse alignment, shows that the 2 mm plaque has a wider through-thickness core in the central region of the cross-section. Furthermore, the 2 mm plaque shows greater a_{11} values in the upper and lower skin regions. Both of these observations can be explained by a blunter through-thickness flow front arising from greater shear thinning in the 2 mm plaque.

Slow Injection Speed (3s fill time)

Fig. 10 shows the through-thickness FOD for the 2 and 4 mm plaques at a slower injection speed and corresponds to the centre lines in the contour plots in Figs 8 and 9. In direct contrast to the high speed injection results, the 4 mm plaque now has higher a_{11} values near the upper and lower walls. As discussed in the previous section on the effect of injection speed, it is likely that in the 2 mm plaque cooling will become important at the slower speed. The shear driven alignment mechanism will be overtaken by the cooling of the melt and freezing in at lower orientation.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has reported on the use of automated image processing & analysis methods for the quantitative measurement of 3D fibre orientation distribution in 20%GF/PP injection moulded plaques. Using these techniques it has been possible to characterise in detail the complex through-thickness FOD including full cross-sectional information. The results of the measurement of FOD at positions near the gate and middle of the plaque, at different injection speeds, have been presented. A relatively thick transverse core region near the gate, resulting from divergent flow, reduces further down the plaque as the shearing forces take effect. The effect of injection speed is minimal in the thicker 4 mm plaque, whilst clear differences were observed in the thinner 2 mm plaque. The difference between FOD in 2mm and 4mm plaques can be explained by shear thinning behaviour at fast injection speed and cooling effects at slow injection speed. A full cross-sectional comparison of the 2mm and 4mm plaques reveals the complexity of FOD showing both through-thickness and cross-width variations. The

powerful methods reported in this paper should enable a greater understanding of the important interaction between processing and fibre orientation to be achieved.

Fig.8: Measured through-thickness orientation tensor components for the 2mm and 4mm plaques at position B for 3 second injection time.

REFERENCES

1. Bright, P. F., and Darlington, M. W., 'Factors Influencing Fibre Orientation and Mechanical Properties in Fibre Reinforced Thermoplastics Injection Mouldings', *Plastics and Rubbers Processing and Application*, Vol. 1, No. 2, 1981, pp. 139-147.
2. Folks, M. J., *Short Fibre-reinforced Thermoplastics*, Chapter 6, Research Student Press, 1982.
3. Hsu, C. Y., Brooks, R., 'Experimental Determination of Orientation in Short Fibre Reinforced Thermoplastics using Image Processing and Analysis', *the 7th European Conference on Composites Materials*, 1996, London, pp.261-266
4. Visilog 4 Manual, *IPE Programmer's Guide*, NOESIS S.A. France, 1993.
5. Hsu, C. Y., *PhD thesis*, Chapter 4, University of Nottingham, 1997 (to be published).
6. Gonzalz, R., Woods, R., *Digital Image Processing*, Chapter 8, Addison-Wesley, 1992.
7. Bay R. S., and Tucker C. L., 'Stereological measurement and Error Estimates for Three-Dimensional Fibre Orientation', *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 1992, Vol. 32, No. 4, pp. 240-253.
8. Hine, P., Duckett, R. A., Davidson, N., Clarke, A. R., 'Modelling of The Elastic Properties of fibre Reinforced Composites. I: Orientation Measurement', *Composites Science and technology*, 1993, Vol. 47, pp.65-73